

Biomaterial: Fascinating Reservoir for Future Stem Cell Based Therapy

Deepika Pal^{1,2*}, Ayushi Chauhan^{1*}, Vanshika Rana^{1*}, Archit Mohan Shukla^{1*}
Akshaya Prakash^{1*}, Drishti Dhall^{1*}, Raxit Tyagi^{1*} and Eliza Chakraborty^{1,2**}

1. Medical Translation Biotechnology Lab, Meerut Institute of Engineering & Technology,
Meerut- 250005, U.P, INDIA

2. DST- Fist Center, Meerut Institute of Engineering & Technology, Meerut- 250005, U.P,
INDIA

* All Authors Contributed Equally

** Corresponding Author

Abstract

Recent translational medicinalera, the stem cell based therapy is most dazzling part as well as bring silver lines to many untreatable diseases. An importantfeature of bioactive material is the uses and effect of Hydrogels in Stem cell-based therapy. The Stem cells have ability to mimic the cell micro- environment and this characteristic made it competent in regenerative medicines,therapies and different application areas. Hydrogels provide many promising solutions to the 3D cell culture viz: spheroid and Organoid based *in vitro*screening models etc. Eventually, Stem cell based tissue engineering opens new avenues to regenerative medicines as well as stem cell-based therapies. Biomedical engineering maybeable to overcome limitations of cell-based therapy in future by exploiting different plant based less toxic and cost-effective biomaterials. This review is focused on combination of stem cell and potential biomaterials based therapy to address worldwideuntreateddiseases.

Keywords: Stem cell therapies, Biomaterial, Bioprinting, Hydrogels, Bioinks and 3D cell culture.

1. Introduction

We presently hold a more prominent plan on the specialized viewpoints and portrayal of biomaterials and its requirements to connect with tissues.Stem cell treatment has demonstrated unbeatable potential in stem cell engineering, although it still poses difficulties in controlling stem cell fate by maintaining microenvironment, synthetic Hydrogels with its characteristics have been developedto provide variable and regulated stem cell fate regulation, considerably improving stem cell therapy's practical application prospects in tissue regeneration.(1)In modern medicine, the current therapies mostly target the prevention, modification and control of illness by chemical or biological molecules (2). The most current developments in biomaterials for stem cell therapy are summarized here. A significant and primary applications of Hydrogel as a biomaterial isthe purposes and impacts in stem cell therapy. These Hydrogels work as a matrix to improve cell viability, which aids in cell proliferation and maintenance.On the basis of recent literature, many years of research and accomplishments, mainstream researchers have fostered various high-level biomaterial systems making out of various properties and utilizations in

medical application for a large number of unexpected problems all throughout the biomedical field. Achievements can be credited to an extensive variety of disciplinary work, which has set the establishment of therapeutic surgeries.(3). A prominent comparison of Hydrogels on the basis of different types of classification has been made by Chaudhary & Chakraborty, 2022*, where we can see how on the basis of origin; Hydrogels are categorized into natural, synthetic, and hybrid (semi-synthetic) on the basis of either homopolymer, copolymer, or semi-interpenetrating network. On the basis of durability, they are either durable (long-lasting) or biodegradable. On the basis of the response to stimuli, they are classified as either intelligent or conventional. On the basis of charge, they are either cationic, anionic, neutral, or amphoteric and on the basis of structure, either amorphous or semi-crystalline in nature.

2. Applications of Hydrogels in Stem cell Therapy

Recent trade, In Stem cell therapy in association with Hydrogels. They are a great match to the natural ECM which is synthesized by the cells as they allow cells to be surrounded in a highly hydrated, structurally intact 3D environment, and thus they are broadly utilized in modern-day tissue engineering and biomanufacturing fields. The need for stable and biocompatible materials is increasing as cell culture advances from 2D to 3D because cells need to be sustained and nourished during the initial growth phase before they can proliferate. In order to make the Hydrogels better suited for printing, the concentration of polymer must be higher to provide structural stability and stiffness. At the same time, the cells need an aqueous environment for their mobility and proliferation. (5) This ability of Hydrogels to absorb water along with retaining structural integrity makes them an important biocompatible material. The Hydrogels are being utilized as bioink material or as cell delivery material due to their extensible properties. Many studies have shown that when different types of cells are encapsulated in a Hydrogel, they tend to survive for longer period of time. (6) Hydrogels must be biocompatible so it does not elicit an immune response or have any effect on the surrounding microenvironment (such as changing pH value or temperature), biodegradable so it degrades over time without leaving any toxic residue so that cells can produce their own ECM as they proliferate, biologically active and should maintain the cell viability so that cell can survive. The Hydrogels should be of such a blend that it is stable at 37°C temperature and at a pH level of 7.4 which is an optimal condition for the survival of cells. The components of the Hydrogel must be either completely metabolized or excreted by the cells in order to reduce the accumulation. The degradation rate should be in a form that the ECM synthesized by the growing cells is supported. The rate of formation of ECM should be equal to the rate of degradation of Hydrogels for a smooth transition if the rate of degradation will be fast, the cells will lose mechanical stability and structural integrity will be jeopardized and if it is slow then the cells will be under shear stress due to increased density. Hence all these factors have to be considered.(7)

Recently, Tissue engineering makes extensive use of both synthetic and natural components. The ability of hybrid Hydrogels to provide controlled cross-linking enables the stability and fixation of the printed shapes and provides a great boost to the applicability of the matrix. Some widely used natural Hydrogels improve the overall properties of the gel such as mechanical, water absorbing, and biochemical properties.(6) Hydrogels are useful in biomedical research because they may function as a growth medium and mimic the extracellular matrix.

3. Applied Mathematical Model

The challenge of consistent development of in-vitro engineered cells can be solved with the use of applied mathematics, whereby specifies input parameters that generate predictable output measurements of tissue maturation. With the measure objective into the connections between molecular transports, polymer breakdown and tissue formation, a mathematical model based on multiphase mixture theory was developed. Hydrogels swelling properties may also be measured using mathematical formulas (4)

$$\text{Swelling} = W_s - W_d / W_d$$

Where W_s is the Hydrogels weight in swollen state and W_d is the Hydrogels weight in the dry state.

$$\text{Swelling} = P/Q * 100$$

Where P is the Hydrogels Weight obtained after drying & Q is the insoluble portion weight after extraction with water.

4. 3D Bioprinting for Stem cell Engineering

The science of tissue engineering is transforming regenerative medicine as technology progresses. Using the precision of 3D bioprinting, living cells are placed on a biomaterial in a layer-by-layer fashion using computational tools. This procedure allows us to deposit cellular material such as cells, proteins, DNA, drug and growth factors with great resolution and precision which enhances the generation of tissues more efficiently when compared with scaffold culture. (8)(9) As the technologies are advancing the ability of bioprinting to mimic the natural cells have been profoundly increased. The wide applicability of bioprinting ranges from transplantation of engineered tissue to regenerative medicine and from high-throughput assays to drug screening. It has been popularized because of its ability to mimic the microenvironment which therein helps in cell growth. In the modern-day society, organ printing still remains a task which poses a great challenge in the field of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine due to the limitations in formation of a functional vasculature of the cells, i.e., formation of arteries, veins and capillaries to provide a stable blood supply to the growing cells along with hindrance in arrangement of various forms of cells to form complex organs which impart stability to the structure along with adding biological functions. (9) Assembling thinner layer tissues, hollow tissues and cartilage are much more possible and have been reproduced using the bioprinting tools and techniques as they do not require vascularization. The precision with which cells are deposited in the particular position on demand is what makes 3D bioprinting a great tool to achieve various operations. Its flexibility to sequentially deposit cells in layers embedded in Hydrogels or in a scaffold free support traces its roots to the additive manufacturing process enabling formation of a 3D structure. (10) As the computational capability of systems improves, computer-aided scaffold topology designing approaches have gained popularity as a feasible option for enhancing the functional capability of tissue engineering. This allows intricate complex designs to be broken into smaller problems and print them with higher precision and controlled architecture. (11) This is achieved by three sequential technical processes: (printing), and post processing. Preprocessing is the first step which ensures the organ designing and formation of the layout using imaging and computer-aided designing as shown in Fig: 1.

Fig: 1 3D Bioprinting of Stem cells(12)

Preprocessing is followed by the printing process, which involves the use of a 3d bioprinter to process the blueprints. The output generated by the bioprinter is then remodeled and subjected to tissue maturation inside a bioreactor, specially designed for the maturation of the printed tissue. (5) It becomes must for the ink to fulfill the biological requirements of cells along with providing the much needed mechanical and physical support to restrain the stresses of printing itself. Hydrogels have been thus found very applicable in this aspect of tissue engineering.

Table:1 Different type of bioinks and their advantage & disadvantages(13),(14)

4.1 Essential characteristics of Bioinks:

Biofabrication or bioprinting is the process to create complex three-dimensional constructs containing biological cells by using formulated bio-ink. In 2022, 3D plotting was first introduced by Landers et al(15). In an extrusion-based method that has the ability to continuously dispense materials. An 'ideal' ink should be able to assure all the biological related needs of the cell. In terms of the physical properties, the

Polymer based bioink	Type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Alginate	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biocompatible • Cheap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimal cell recognition and adhesion. • Low mechanical strength.
Gelatin	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages cellular growth. • Thermo responsive sol-gel transition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liquefies at physiological temperature. • Poor mechanical strength.
Hyaluronic Acid	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodegradable • Biocompatible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly hydrophilic. • Not mechanically stable.
Agarose	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produces constructs with good shape fidelity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viscosity plugging
Collagen	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance cellular function/attachment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor mechanical properties
Cellulose	Natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced toxicity • Biocompatibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor dissolution
Polyethylene glycol(PEG)	Synthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biocompatible • Hydrophilic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor mechanical strength • Poor adhesion
Poly(lactic acid)(PLA)	Synthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excellent mechanical strength • Biodegradable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low hydrophilicity • Poor cell interaction and adhesion.
Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL)	Synthetic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biocompatible • Thermoplastic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of biological properties

ink should be able to assure all the biological related needs of the cell and express gel-like characteristics or should be adequately viscous to dispense as a free-standing filament. In terms of mechanical

properties, the individually printed filament needs to have sufficient strength in order to retain its structural unity after the printing process. And the final outcome should not be toxic which must permit cell adhesion and proliferation. Such properties must usher the initiation of tissues which provides sufficient mechanical strength and robustness along with retaining the mechanics of tissue-matching in a tuneful way, the adjustment in the process of gelation and stabilization in order to support the structures, mimicking the natural microenvironment for the tissue resulting in biocompatibility and if necessary biodegradability. (16) The properties of bioink prior to and after gelation is a crucial factor for its printability, containing features like feasible skeletal resolution, shape accuracy and survival of the cells. The bioinks with low viscosity could be quite challenging. The rheological properties of these bioinks are generally not specified by the manufacturer. (17) The substance widely used as bioinks involve metals, ceramics and thermoplastic polymers. A bioink is considered ideal which contains the properties like stability, high mechanical integrity, printability, insolubility in the media used for culturing along with non-toxic, regeneration of tissue and non-immunogenicity. Moreover, the materials used as bioink must be quickly producible and commercially available. (18) In order to overcome these challenges, the materials based on dynamic covalent supramolecular and materials which are responsive are currently being produced to be used as bioink for the process of bioprinting. The material used as bioink is vital as it provides the array of biochemical properties (like growth factors, chemokines or adhesion factors) and physical properties (i.e. structural and mechanical properties, interstitial flow) that promotes survival of cells, differentiation and motility. (19)

4.2 Different types of polymers used for Bioink:

Bioinks formed by polymers are widely used because of properties like biocompatibility, low cost, secure working and degradation. Another polymer used which is water-soluble is also used as bioinks for bioprinting and is known as Hydrogels. Hydrogels are used for their chemical configuration and their ability to offer a favorable environment for three-dimensional cell growth. A Hydrogel is basically a group of polymeric networks arranged in a three-dimensional manner. Different polymers like Collagen are one of the greatest attractions of polymers. It has been widely studied for its implementation in tissue engineering. Collagen is a naturally occurring biocompatible protein with a triple-helical structure. Fibrin is also used as a material for scaffolding in a broad-ranging of tissue engineering applications mainly in vascular grafts. Fibrin is known to be one of the most vital proteins included in the processes like wound healing and blood clotting. Different types of fibers of silk produced by *Bombyx mori* (*B. mori*) are being used in tissue engineering. Silk fibroin scaffolds have various advantages over other scaffolds such as mechanical stability, increased biocompatibility, non-toxicity and luster. (18) A well-known natural polymer known as Chitosan is also used in tissue engineering. Chitons have been effectively used due to its properties like low cost, antibacterial, biodegradability, and biocompatibility. Also, another polymer known as Alginate is a natural polysaccharide amongst the popular Hydrogels. Alginate consists of properties like biocompatibility, low price and is also compatible with different methods of printing. Agarose has also been extensively used as a biopolymer for various biomedical applications. It has properties like mechanical toughness, tunable rigidity, and permeability to water. (20) Gum acts as a thickening agent by improving the viscoelastic properties of Hydrogels in order to transmit them the desired mechanical strength. Gums are hydrophilic in nature and are easy to blend with other biomaterials as well as bioactive compounds. (21) Aloe Vera in the form of Hydrogels has a lot of desirable properties like transportation of nutrients for improved proliferation of cells and anti-microbial effects. (22) In 3D bioprinting, synthetic bioinks may produce scaffolds with excellent mechanical strength. Most synthetic

Hydrogels lack adequate cell sites for active binding, resulting in an unsuitable environment for cells and cell survival activities. Table 1 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of such polymers. (23)

5. Biomolecule-based Bioink:

The increasing and often complex need for bioinks has pushed the researchers to formulate new methodologies for embodying the bioinks with the best qualities and characteristics. Bioinks created by the traditionally 3D printed Hydrogels were mediocre in both counts i.e. mechanical properties and cytocompatibility.(24)With the expansion of 3D bioprinting, there is a substantial increase in the advancement of novel techniques to reinforce bioinks with additional or external components using advanced technologies. A few of these bioink reinforcement approaches include (24)(25)

- Nanomaterial
- Microparticles and Microspheres:
- Nanofibers/ Bionanomaterials such as carbon-based nanoparticles (CNTs);

5.1 Nanomaterials:

Nanomaterials have been exploited in a variety of therapeutic applications, including imaging, cancer treatment, and drug delivery, etc. Moreover, they have been used to enhance bioink functionalities like controlling the cell behavior and activity, improving printability, electrical conductivity and stimuli responsiveness. By utilizing the nano effect, bioinks can be employed to produce constructs with enhanced properties. For instance, using human platelet derivatives and adding cellulose crystals, a bioink was produced that had the capability to generate 3D printed constructs with exceptional cell sustainability.(24)(25)

5.2 Microparticles and Microspheres:

A microparticle, ranging in size from 1 to 1000 micrometers, can also be used in 3D bioprinting applications to deliver substances. Moreover, these particles can be used either to deliver drugs or as additives to enhance the properties of bioinks. For example, Kim et al. synthesized a smart bioink(dCEM powder-based bioink) by decellularizing and free-milling the liver of a pig. This smart bioink showed excellent results in terms of layer stacking for 3D bioprinting as compared to the traditional bioink. The smart bioink that includes microparticles and microspheres delivery systems shows exceptional performance in terms of physical and chemical stability, simple and reproducible manufacturing, maximum encapsulation and maximum yield, and flowability (26)

5.3 Nanofibres/CNTs:

In recent years, nanofibres/ nanocrystals and carbon-based nanoparticles (CNTs and graphene) have been widely exploited in bioink reinforcement investigations as they provide improved mechanical and chemical properties to the scaffold when blended with the bioink. For example, for the purpose of TE, alginate is covalently bonded to carboxyl-functionalized multiwalled CNTs to improve a collagen scaffold's mechanical characteristics and electrical conductivity. Bioprinted scaffolds containing CNTs showed increased cell proliferation and differentiation; making them appropriate for myocardial TE

applications. In addition, graphene and its derivatives, when reinforced with Hydrogels, provide improved electrical properties which are widely adapted in various biomedical applications and drug delivery systems. Promising results have been achieved in an attempt to improve printability and mechanical properties in an alginate bioink using cellulose nanofibres. Studies have shown that even a small amount of nanofibers (2-3%) improves a great deal of bioink mechanical properties (such as compressive modulus). (24)

6. Conclusion

The advanced technology and groundbreaking work in the tissue culture field has made it feasible for stem cells to be used in biomedical engineering. The use of stem cells in the field of medicine has been of great importance as they possess a great deal of potential to cause an effective treatment which will not be rejected as other transplants. The ability of stem cells to form any cell upon differentiation based on the growth factors provide flexibility in the treatment. The incorporation of the stem cell-based therapy with the biomaterials based bio matrix have been extensively exploited as they're very suitable to deliver and also biocompatible thus does not cause harm to the cells. The broad applicability of biomaterials and extensive use of these Hydrogels in therapeutic benefit has been summarized in this paper. Stem Cell therapy has provided a great opportunity and promising results in the field of tissue regeneration which enables the formation of new organs and tissues. The advancement of technology in the field of 3D bioprinting has made it possible to precisely control the deposition of cells in a layer-by-layer manner allowing the formation of complex and intricate biological designs. The assistance of computer-aided designing tools has provided a great addition to the field of bioprinting with advanced imaging techniques to capture in-depth images of the tissues and organs and to replicate them in a 3D construct for optimized functional replication of the cells. Bioprinting has been widely used in research-based enclosures to optimize the efficiency of the tissues that are being produced using this technique, but the clinical use of bioprinting will lead to the formation of important tissues such as neuronal, cardiovascular, renal, retinal, and musculoskeletal which require the functional vasculature that is the major current limitation of this technology. There is a need to find a biocompatible material that is capable to sustain the mechanical and structural needs of these constructs. Bioinks and Hydrogels have provided flexibility with stability to the biomaterials which allow the construct to sustain living cells for a longer period of time providing a growth environment to the cells. These latest advancements have shaped the technology in a manner that provides opportunities for finding solutions to the limitations of scaling of the production of tissues and organs. There is a wide potential for biomaterials in stem cells-based therapy technologies.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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